

Epicardial adipose tissue produces L-3-hydroxybutyrate in advanced heart failure: direct analysis of fat metabolic remodeling

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ABSTRACT

Background: Heart failure (HF) progression involves complex metabolic and multi-organ alterations, but the specific adaptations in adipose tissue are not fully understood.

Aims: We aimed to characterize the metabolic remodeling of epicardial (EAT) and subcutaneous (SAT) adipose tissues in HF with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), focusing on lipid metabolism, fatty acid oxidation, and ketogenesis.

Methods: Clinical and metabolomic profiling were performed on metabolically stable controls ($n = 34$), patients with mild HFrEF ($n = 45$), and severe HFrEF ($n = 129$). Metabolomics profiling identified over 800 metabolites in EAT and SAT. Clustering and pathway enrichment analyses defined depot-specific metabolic shifts across HF stages, while gene expression analyses provided mechanistic support.

Results: Advancing HF was associated with declining cardiac function, systemic congestion, and a metabolic shift toward catabolism. Metabolomics revealed depot-specific adaptations: SAT transitioned smoothly to enhanced lipolysis, whereas EAT demonstrated impaired triacylglycerol replenishment and disrupted final turn of β -oxidation spiral. Both depots increased reliance on acylcarnitine degradation and lipolysis; however, EAT was uniquely characterized by late-stage impairment in mitochondrial and peroxisomal fatty acid oxidation, leading to elevation of 3-hydroxybutyrate and hydroxybutyrylcarnitine tissue levels. Ex vivo analyses of EAT explants showed significantly increased fraction of L-3-hydroxybutyrate enantiomer, produced by EAT, compared to D-3-hydroxybutyrate enantiomer originating from the liver.

Conclusions: HF progression drives major, depot-specific metabolic remodeling in adipose tissue. In advanced HF, EAT shows impaired fatty acid oxidation and enhanced local production of L-3-hydroxybutyrate in the vicinity of myocardium, highlighting the close metabolic cooperation in nutrient supply between EAT and the heart muscle through the coronary circulation.

1. Introduction

HF is defined as a complex, multifactorial syndrome arising from multiple comorbidities, with ischemic heart disease, hypertension,

obesity, and diabetes as key contributors. The prevalence of HF is increasing. In developed countries, approximately 2–3 % of the adult population suffers from HF, with an additional 2 % remaining undiagnosed [1,2]. The prognosis of HF is poor, with 50 % mortality within 5

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years of the first HF manifestation [3]. HF exists in two phenotypes that differ by: (i) impaired diastolic function in HF with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) and (ii) predominant systolic dysfunction and intense neurohumoral activation in HFrEF, showing relatively worse prognosis [4].

Numerous studies suggest that the endocrine dysfunction of adipose tissue and systemic and local subclinical inflammation are crucial pathophysiological mechanisms linking obesity, diabetes, and HF [5]. The links of adipose tissue to cardiac function are complex and poorly understood. On one side, excessive adiposity represents a strong risk factor for HF and particularly for HFpEF. On the other side, healthy adipose tissue supports cardiac function by serving as a source of free fatty acids (FA), the predominant metabolic substrate of cardiomyocytes [6].

Different adipose tissue depots may have distinctive relations to cardiac function. SAT metabolism is essential for maintaining overall energy balance, providing FA, and regulating various physiological processes. EAT represents a specific white fat depot, which is located between the myocardium and the visceral pericardium. It has distinct characteristics that differentiate it from other visceral fat depots. It is particularly concentrated in the atrioventricular and interventricular grooves, as well as above the walls of the ventricles and atria [7]. Unlike other adipose depots with distinct boundaries (such as fascia), EAT has a close anatomical and functional relationship with the heart muscle, sharing unimpeded microcirculation supplied by the coronary arteries with the myocardial tissue. By close connection, EAT can directly affect the adjacent myocardium or coronary vessels via paracrine and vaso-crine mechanisms [8,9]. EAT also has different developmental origins than SAT, originating from the epicardium and being perfused by coronary vasculature rather than systemic vessels [10].

Patients with obesity-related HFpEF exhibit EAT dysfunction, characterized by increased EAT thickness and a biological shift toward synthesizing proinflammatory cytokines, which directly disrupt myocardial structure and function [11,12]. They also demonstrate evidence of systemic inflammation and abnormalities in cardiac filling, often appearing long before clinical presentation [13].

However, there is considerably less data on the relationship between EAT and HFrEF. Studies have indicated that individuals with HFrEF have reduced EAT mass and thickness compared to healthy controls or those with HFpEF, with an opposing relation of EAT thickness to prognosis and HF severity in HFpEF and HFrEF [14,15], probably reflecting cardiac cachexia [15,16]. It is likely that different stages of HF (none, early, or late) have distinctive responses in adipose tissue depots.

Our aim was to identify molecules and related metabolic pathways in adipose tissue associated with the presence of HFrEF. We hypothesized that the metabolism of EAT will be affected by the presence of HFrEF differently from SAT, and these changes will be influenced by the stages of HF progression. To examine this hypothesis, we compared clinical parameters, plasma samples, and SAT and EAT tissue explants from control subjects and the patients with mild HFrEF (MHF, undergoing cardiac surgery) and severe HFrEF (SHF, undergoing heart transplantation or mechanical assist device implantation). We have performed targeted and untargeted metabolomic and lipidomic profiling of EAT and SAT samples together with gene expression analysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study population

This observational cross-sectional study, EPILOGUE, enrolled 174 HF patients and 34 control participants between [5/2019 and 5/2022] (see Fig. S1, CONSORT flow diagram). The HF cohort comprised two groups: (i) MHF patients ($n = 45$) with mild HF (NYHA I-II, LVEF $<50\%$, BNP <200 pmol/l) undergoing CABG/valve surgery, and (ii) SHF patients ($n = 129$) with severe HF (NYHA III-IV, LVEF $<30\%$, brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) ≥ 200 pmol/l) undergoing left ventricular assist device

(LVAD) implantation or transplantation, with LVAD patients receiving longitudinal assessments at implantation and explantation. The control group ($n = 34$) consisted of patients without HF (LVEF $>50\%$, BNP <10.2 pmol/l) undergoing elective cardiac surgery. Participants were stratified by cardiac cachexia ($\geq 5\%$ unintentional weight loss in 6 months), HF etiology, and diabetes status. Exclusion criteria for all groups included acute coronary syndrome, active malignancy, and systemic inflammation, with additional HF exclusion for controls. All participants underwent preoperative assessments including anthropometry, blood/urine biomarkers (NT-proBNP, hsCRP, cytokines), and echocardiography. Adipose tissues and blood plasma were collected into cryovials and stored at -80°C until the extraction. None of the patients suffered from thyroid disease, malignancy, acute or chronic kidney disease, or acute infection. All participants provided written informed consent before enrolling in the study. The patients did not receive compensation, as the samples were collected during scheduled surgeries. The study was approved by the Human Ethics Review Board at the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine (IKEM) in Prague, Czech Republic (ethical approval code G-18-36). The research was conducted following the principles outlined in the WMA Declaration of Helsinki.

Four SHF patients for the experiment with 3-hydroxybutyrate (3-OHB) release from EAT explants were selected based on the same criteria as for the main cohort. The validation cohort of SHF patients has been published before [17].

2.2. Surgical methods

Samples of EAT and SAT were obtained intraoperatively as part of standard cardiac surgical procedures performed via median sternotomy. See Supplemental methods.

2.3. Biochemical analysis

Blood samples were collected before the start of surgery, after a fasting period of 6 to 12 h. The serum or plasma samples were processed as before [18], and aliquots were stored at -80°C . Biochemical parameters were measured, and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol was calculated using standard laboratory methods in the IKEM Laboratory Methods Division [19].

2.4. Sample extraction for lipidomics and metabolomics

Adipose tissue samples (10–25 mg) and plasma (25 μl) were processed using a biphasic solvent system of cold methanol, methyl *tert*-butyl ether (MTBE), and water as before [18]. See Supplemental methods.

2.5. Untargeted lipidomic and metabolomic profiling

Lipidomic and metabolomic profiling of samples was conducted using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) systems consisting of a Vanquish ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) coupled to a Q Exactive Plus mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) operated in the positive and negative ion mode, as described previously [20]. See Supplemental methods.

2.6. Gene expression analysis

Total RNA was isolated from EAT and SAT samples using the RNeasy Lipid Tissue Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The transcript levels were evaluated using quantitative reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR) analysis, following previously established methods [21].

2.7. 3-Hydroxybutyrate production in adipose tissue

EAT explants were thoroughly washed in phosphate-buffered saline to remove residual blood and debris. Subsequently, explants were transferred to 12-well plates and incubated in 2 ml of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium per well at 37 °C for 90 min. Following incubation, media samples were collected and stored at −80 °C until analysis. The concentration of total 3-OHB and lactate released into the media was quantified using LC-MS, as described above. The separation of D-3-OHB and L-3-OHB was achieved through derivatization [22]. See Supplemental methods.

2.8. MILLIPLEX human metabolic hormone panel magnetic beads multiplex assay

MILLIPLEX human metabolic panel V3 14-plex kit (HMH3-34K; Merck Millipore Corporation, MA, USA), utilizing antibodies to human insulin, glucagon, interleukin (IL-6), and C-peptide, was used to screen human blood plasma samples.

2.9. Data analysis and statistics

Data processing was performed using MetaboAnalyst 6.0 (log10 data transformation and Pareto-scaling). Plotly was used to draw complex plots. Student's *t*-test analysis, one-way ANOVA (Tukey's multiple comparisons test), and Welch's one-way ANOVA (Dunnett's multiple comparisons test) were used to compare study groups, and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant. VSClust was used for metabolome clustering [23]. LORA was used to perform an over-representation analysis [24].

3. Results

3.1. Clinical characterization

The study cohort reveals a distinct difference between metabolically stable controls (CTRL) and MHF, as well as between MHF and SHF patients (Table 1). MHF patients had significantly higher levels of plasma BNP and interleukin-6 (IL-6), and a lower left ventricular ejection fraction. As HF severity increases, patients experience worsening cardiac function, with reduced ejection fraction and signs of systemic congestion such as hepatorenal dysfunction (MELD-XI, eGFR) and elevated inflammatory markers. Metabolic changes are pronounced in SHF patients, where a marked reduction in insulin levels and the insulin/glucagon ratio reflects a starvation-like, catabolic state, as highlighted by the negative trend lines of BNP and BMI (Fig. S2). Additionally, the insulin/C-peptide ratio is decreased in HF, indicating enhanced insulin clearance. These metabolic alterations coincide with a higher prevalence of cachexia and highlight the shift from insulin resistance to catabolic dominance. Treatment intensity also rises with disease severity, including higher doses of diuretics and greater use of neuro-hormonal blockade, underscoring the complex, multi-organ impact of advanced HF.

3.2. Metabolomic profiling revealed dynamic changes in adipose tissue metabolism during HF progression

To explore the adaptations of EAT and SAT to altered metabolic status during HF progression, we performed metabolomics analysis and annotated over 800 metabolites (polar compounds and lipids) in both depots. In order to explore the dynamic changes of the metabolipidome, we performed clustering analysis and defined pseudo-time profiles of metabolite levels as a sequence of CTRL, MHF, and SHF states (Fig. 1). These profiles mimic the temporal progression of HF. The clustering of EAT data resulted in six different scenarios: a metabolite gradually increases, gradually decreases, increases only in the later stage, etc., or metabolites that do not fit any scenario (Fig. 1A). The calculated shapes

Table 1
Baseline characteristics of the study population.

	CTRL group	MHF group	SHF group	<i>p</i> -Value, one-way ANOVA	Significantly different groups, Tukey's multiple comparisons test $p < 0.05$
Number of subjects (n)	34	45	129		
LV EF (%)	58.2 ± 1.12	37.9 ± 1.46	21.4 ± 0.64	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; CTRL > MHF; MHF > SHF
NYHA	1.88 ± 0.35	2.40 ± 0.46	3.53 ± 0.50		
Age (years)	64.9 ± 1.2	67.6 ± 1.18	54.2 ± 1.13	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
History of hypertension (n, %)	8 (4.3)	13 (28.9)	31 (27.6)		
HF etiology (ischemic/non-ischemic) (n, %)	–	Ischemic – 31 (68.9)	Ischemic – 52 (40.3)		
		Other – 14(31.1)	Other – 77 (59.7)		
EAT thickness (mm)	5.70 ± 0.86	4.17 ± 0.44	4.70 ± 0.23	0.1419	
Cachexia (n, %)	2 (5.9)	3 (6.6)	31 (24.0)		
Furosemide daily dose (mg)	2.35	40.25	184.67		
ACE or ANRI or ARB (n, %)	25 (73.5)	36 (80)	59 (45.7)		
Gliflozins (n, %)	0	1 (2.7)	22 (19.8)		
MRA (n, %)	2 (5.9)	26 (57.8)	95 (73.6)		
BB (n, %)	25 (73.5)	36 (80)	86 (66.7)		
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.9 ± 0.53	31 ± 0.84	27.4 ± 0.39	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
Glycemia/ (mmol/l)	6.45 ± 0.33	6.99 ± 0.52	6.41 ± 0.19	0.3916	NS
HbA1c/(mmol/mol)	45.9 ± 1.64	51.3 ± 2.17	44.2 ± 0.88	0.0014	MHF > SHF
T2DM (n, %)	27 (79.4)	32 (71.1)	48 (42.8)		
Insulin/(ng/l)	764.7 ± 91.1	736.7 ± 74.5	479.1 ± 35.2	0.0002	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
Glucagon/(ng/l)	51.1 ± 4.34	48.1 ± 3.19	55.6 ± 3.3	0.3296	NS
C-peptide/(µg/l)	1.85 ± 0.12	2.02 ± 0.16	2.9 ± 0.16	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
Insulin/glucagon ratio	15.6 ± 1.82	14.8 ± 1.62	8.28 ± 0.64	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
Insulin/C-peptide ratio	0.39 ± 0.036	0.41 ± 0.045	0.18 ± 0.013	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
Triacylglycerols/ (mmol/l)	1.58 ± 0.13	1.61 ± 0.12	1.41 ± 0.07	0.2672	NS
Cholesterol total/(mmol/l)	3.58 ± 0.17	4.01 ± 0.16	3.37 ± 0.09	0.0018	MHF > SHF

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

	CTRL group	MHF group	SHF group	p-Value, one-way ANOVA	Significantly different groups, Tukey's multiple comparisons test $p < 0.05$
Cholesterol LDL/(mmol/l)	1.92 ± 0.15	2.29 ± 0.13	1.99 ± 0.07	0.0730	NS
CRP/(mg/l)	3.25 ± 0.88	3.66 ± 0.48	30.4 ± 4.58	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
GGT/(μkat/l)	0.75 ± 0.12	0.83 ± 0.11	2.47 ± 0.32	0.0002	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
IL-6/(ng/l)	4.69 ± 0.62	7.5 ± 0.95	27 ± 2.47	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; CTRL < MHF; MHF < SHF
BNP (ng/l)	39.4 ± 5.18	353.2 ± 62.0	1455.2 ± 109.6	<0.0001	CTRL < MHF; MHF < SHF
ALP/(μkat/l)	1.08 ± 0.05	1.24 ± 0.05	1.98 ± 0.17	0.0009	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
ALT/(μkat/l)	0.59 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.04	1.71 ± 0.42	0.0818	NS
AST/(μkat/l)	0.46 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.06	2.67 ± 1.25	0.3477	NS
MELD-XI score	6.39 ± 0.74	6.61 ± 0.66	12.5 ± 0.53	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
eGFR	84.2 ± 2.57	78.9 ± 2.61	70.61 ± 2.60	0.0067	CTRL < SHF
Heart rate (bpm)	69.4 ± 3.27	68.5 ± 2.17	86.6 ± 1.71	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
EF CM (%)	42.1 ± 3.40	44.2 ± 2.52	21.3 ± 0.84	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
LVEEm mean (mm)	9.52 ± 0.91	14.1 ± 1.66	15.7 ± 0.85	0.0157	CTRL < SHF
RVD1 (mm)	35.2 ± 1.23	36.8 ± 1.67	45.2 ± 0.83	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
RVTAPSE (mm)	22.4 ± 1.79	20.6 ± 1.12	15.3 ± 0.47	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
RVTDI (cm/s)	12.5 ± 0.87	11.4 ± 0.50	8.51 ± 0.30	<0.0001	CTRL > SHF; MHF > SHF
RAV (ml)	15.0 ± 0.98	17.5 ± 1.33	25.4 ± 1.11	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF
TrGradSystMax (mmHg)	24.4 ± 2.95	32.3 ± 4.56	38.9 ± 1.47	0.0111	CTRL < SHF
VCI size (mm)	14. ± 0.98	16.4 ± 0.82	22.1 ± 0.60	<0.0001	CTRL < SHF; MHF < SHF

BMI, body mass index; BNP, brain natriuretic peptide; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LV EF, left ventricular ejection fraction; CRP, C-reactive protein; GGT, gamma-glutamyltransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; HbA1c, haemoglobin A1c; IL-6, interleukin 6; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; Apo B, apolipoprotein B; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus; ACEi, angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitor; ARNI, angiotensin receptor neprilysin inhibitor; ARB, angiotensin II receptor blocker; MRA, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist; BB, beta-blockers; MELD-XI, Model for End-stage Liver Disease; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; EF CM, Ejection Fraction (by Simpson/CM); LVEEm mean, Left Ventricular Endocardial Measurement (mean); RVD1, Right Ventricular Basal Diameter; RVTAPSE, Right

Ventricular Tricuspid Annular Plane Systolic Excursion; RVTDI, Right Ventricular Tissue Doppler Imaging Systolic Velocity (S); RAV, Right Atrial Volume; TrGradSystMax, Tricuspid Regurgitation Maximum Systolic Pressure Gradient; VCI Size, Vena Cava Inferior Size.

of these scenarios are shown in Fig. 1B (middle panel). Each cluster consisted of 34–402 metabolites, and lipids were the major components.

Next, we performed lipid over-representation analysis for each cluster, defining the characteristic lipid class or structural motif (Fig. 1C). The cluster #1 (late increase) was significantly enriched with fatty acyl carnitines and diacylglycerols (markers of ongoing β -oxidation and lipolysis); cluster #2 (gradual increase) was composed of phospholipids and ceramides; cluster #3 (gradual decrease) was composed of polyunsaturated triacylglycerols (markers of advanced lipolysis); cluster #4 (temporary increase) was composed of triacylglycerols with short acyl chains (markers of de novo lipogenesis); and cluster #5 (late decrease) contained unsaturated triacylglycerols with ether-linked acyl chains. Cluster #1 contained a sufficient number of polar metabolites, and thus, we performed pathway enrichment analysis using the Small Molecule Pathway Database (SMPDB) as a reference base. Although lipids cannot be completely mapped into SMPDB terms, we found significant over-representation of the carnitine synthesis pathway (Fig. 1D).

In detail, levels of free carnitine increased over time, particularly in EAT, indicating higher demands on the β -oxidation machinery (Fig. 1F). The marker of FA oxidation defects was increased in EAT (Fig. 1G). Diacylglycerols as lipolytic intermediates were increased mainly in SAT and at a later stage (Fig. 1H).

Parallel analysis of SAT and EAT data highlighted differences between the depots and HF stages (Fig. 1E, bottom part). The progress of lipolysis was smoother in SAT than in EAT, documented by anti-parallel profiles of clusters #2 and #3. The changes in phospholipids happened later in SAT than in EAT, and more phospholipids were perturbed in SAT. The transient increase of short-chain triacylglycerols was accompanied by TG-estolides (FAHFA-TG) in SAT only (Fig. 1E, cluster #4).

The analyses jointly identified acylcarnitine, carnitine synthesis, and lipolysis pathways as the prevailing drivers of metabolic changes in both depots. While SAT showed a smooth transition from the resting to the highly lipolytic state, EAT showed time impairment between the lipolysis and subsequent β -oxidation of FA (Fig. 1F-H).

3.3. Triacylglycerol lipolysis and reesterification are impaired in EAT during the late stage of HF

The rate of lipolysis, or the breakdown of triacylglycerols and production of free FAs, did not differ significantly between the CTRL and MHF groups. Levels of triacylglycerols in both SAT and EAT dropped significantly only in the SHF groups (Fig. 2A), and the levels of free FA increased mainly in SAT (Fig. 2B). Detailed analysis of triacylglycerol composition explained the apparent inconsistency between the absolute levels and dynamic changes in cluster #3 (Fig. 2C). At the MHF state, short-chain triacylglycerols were increased, and long-chain (and more unsaturated) triacylglycerols were decreased, which was in agreement with the clustering results. However, the main core of triacylglycerols remained inert (grey bubbles in Fig. 2C and brown sections in Fig. 1). At the SHF state, SAT was able to synthesize more of the new, short-chain triacylglycerols (red circles in Fig. 2C) while the lipolytic pathway (blue circles in Fig. 2C) dominated the EAT profile.

This comparative analysis revealed that EAT is unable to replenish and dynamically regulate fat reserves at the later stages of HF, and that lipolysis and FA oxidation are specifically altered in EAT.

3.4. Fatty acid β -oxidation is impaired in EAT despite elevated carnitine synthesis

Based on the results of cluster analysis emphasizing acylcarnitine

Fig. 1. Pseudo-time profiling of adipose tissue metabolipidome during heart failure progression.

(A) EAT metabolipidome clustered according to pseudo-time profile: CTRL > MHF > SHF. Metabolites were separated into five distinct clusters (#1 - #5), and 402 metabolite profiles were not associated with any cluster.

(B) Cluster patterns. Data are medians of individual profiles \pm range. Cluster composition was assigned according to HMDB.

(C) Lipid over-representation analysis. Significantly enriched lipid structural terms for each cluster are shown in the color-coded bubbles. (Fisher's exact test, Benjamini/Hochberg FDR < 0.05). Very important lipid defines the most representative lipid of the cluster.

(D) Pathway enrichment analysis using the SMPDB human database for cluster #1. Metabolite names were converted into HMDB ID.

(E) SAT metabolipidome clustered according to time profiles, as above.

(F) Levels of free carnitine in SAT and EAT. Data are means \pm S.E., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(G) Ratio of free carnitine and acylcarnitines as a marker of mitochondrial β -oxidation. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(H) Levels of diacylglycerols, sum of all species. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

Fig. 2. Triacylglycerol profiling in adipose tissues.

(A) Levels of triacylglycerols, sum of all species. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(B) Levels of FA, sum of all species. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(C) Bubble plots of triacylglycerol species sorted according to the number of carbon atoms and double bonds. The size of the circle represents levels. The red color indicates a significantly increased species, while the blue color indicates a significantly decreased species compared to the control group (represented by the grey color). Data are transformed (square root of mean). One-way ANOVA/Tukey pairwise post hoc test, $\alpha = 0.05$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

metabolism and lipolysis, we decided to focus on the carnitine synthesis and acylcarnitine pathways. Free carnitine is important for the smooth transport of liberated FA into mitochondria, and its shortage might limit β -oxidation efficiency. Levels of lysine and all intermediates in the de novo synthesis of carnitine were increased (Fig. 3A), and free carnitine was highly elevated, especially in EAT at the SHF state. However, adipose tissue lacks γ -butyrobetaine hydroxylase, the final enzyme required for carnitine synthesis, which is exclusive to the liver and kidneys. Under conditions of carnitine shortage, γ -butyrobetaine can be transported to the liver for carnitine synthesis, which can then be returned to adipose tissue [25].

Carnitine is also critical for the import of acyl-CoA intermediates of FA degradation, which originated outside mitochondria. Using the metabolic scheme of fatty acyl-CoA degradation via β -oxidation spirals (Fig. 3B), we designed a parallel scheme containing acylcarnitines, which are in metabolic balance with the acyl-CoAs (Fig. 3C). Under optimal conditions, the individual steps in the β -oxidation pathway should be in mass balance; thus, the number of incoming precursors should equal the number of outgoing products. Therefore, the levels of successive acylcarnitines should highly correlate with each other. We used crescent graphs to illustrate the correlation coefficients. A clear difference between SAT and EAT was observed at the crossroad of saturated FA degradation and the incoming branch of oleic acid degradation (C14 vs C12 bottleneck), suggesting that, in contrast to SAT, the enzymatic machinery in EAT is either impaired or alternative oxidation intermediates interfere, independent of HF (Fig. 3C).

This suggests an imbalance between mitochondrial and peroxisomal FA oxidation. This imbalance is partially compensated by the import of carnitine, which supports the coupling of the FA oxidation pathway.

3.5. EAT uniquely integrates mitochondrial and peroxisomal β - and ω -oxidation pathways

While the majority of FA are degraded via β -oxidation in

mitochondria, peroxisomal β - and ω -oxidation specializes in very long chain or highly unsaturated FA and acetyl-CoAs, and shorter acyl-CoAs are transported to mitochondria. The final product of β -oxidation, acetyl-CoA, can enter several metabolic pathways (Fig. 4A).

We measured the mRNA of genes involved in both types of oxidation and combined the gene and metabolite profiles in a WikiPathways map (Fig. S3). Gene expression analysis showed that EAT relied on peroxisomal oxidation more than SAT (Fig. 4B), and the expression of key oxidation genes dramatically dropped, especially in EAT, at the later stage of HF (Fig. 4C), which was accompanied by an increase of dicarboxylic acylcarnitine intermediates (Fig. 4D). However, the pathway was able to process substrates, as evidenced by the presence of shorter-chain dicarboxylic intermediates (Fig. 4E). No changes in key gene expression were observed for mitochondrial β -oxidation machinery (Fig. 4F).

Interestingly, levels of butyrylcarnitine (CAR 4:0) and hydroxybutyrylcarnitine (CAR 4:0;OH) were significantly elevated in EAT at the later stage of HF, and this increase was disproportional to the increase of acetylcarnitine (Fig. 4G). This suggests an alternative metabolic fate of short-chain acyl-CoAs generated during the last round of β -oxidation. Excess acetyl-CoA from peroxisomes can invert the metabolic balance, and the short-chain intermediates may prematurely exit the β -oxidation spiral as butyryl-CoA and L-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA, which can be further converted to carnitine forms or free carboxylic acids (CAR 4:0 and CAR 4:0;OH, or butyrate and L-3-OHB) (Fig. 4A).

Moreover, the impaired lipolysis in EAT can be linked to a disrupted balance of anti- and pro-lipolytic stimuli, documented by simultaneous downregulation of both natriuretic peptides' receptors, insulin receptor, and β 2-adrenergic receptor (Fig. S4).

3.6. EAT produces L-3-OHB for the heart metabolism

It is known that advanced HF is associated with increased circulating ketone bodies (mainly 3-OHB) coming from the liver, the conventional

Fig. 3. Carnitine synthesis pathway and fatty acid β -oxidation in SAT and EAT.

(A) Levels of metabolites within the pathway of carnitine biosynthesis. Data are means \pm S.D. $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(B) Schematic representation of the FA β -oxidation pathway. Acyl-CoA species are labeled according to Lipid Shorthand Nomenclature for MS-Derived Lipid Structures. Scheme represents degradation of (i) oleic acid (C18:1) to acetyl-CoA, and (ii) saturated FA from arachidic acid (C20:0) to acetyl-CoA (■).

(C) Correlation plots (crescent moon plots) showing correlations within acylcarnitines at connected steps of β -oxidation spirals. Acylcarnitines are used as stable substitutes for acyl-CoA species. Blue color, SAT; red color, EAT. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

organ of ketogenesis [26,27]. Ketone body utilization is increased in failing hearts, and these alternative substrates can compensate for diminished oxidation of FA [28].

Indeed, levels of 3-OHB and acetoacetate in plasma were increased, especially in the SHF group, together with the free plasma NEFA levels, which serve as their precursors in hepatic ketogenesis (Fig. 5A). Surprisingly, tissue levels of 3-OHB were high in EAT already in the control group and further increased in the SHF group (Fig. 5B). This observation motivated us to perform an experiment and test whether EAT explants synthesize 3-OHB. Pieces of EAT from SHF patients were incubated ex vivo for 90 min, and 3-OHB production into the medium was monitored along with lactate production. The EAT explants were viable, as evidenced by rising but very low lactate concentrations (Fig. S5), and they secreted 3-OHB (Fig. 5C), which was positively identified by LC-MS/MS (Figs. 5D, S6).

The expression of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA synthase 2 (HMGCS2), the main ketogenic enzyme in the liver, was negligible in EAT, ruling out its direct contribution and EAT ketogenesis. Alternatively, a process of reversed ketolysis, in which the direction of ketolysis enzymatic machinery in EAT is inverted due to excess acetyl-CoA, could increase 3-OHB levels. However, the systemic 3-OHB gradient ($\sim 32 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in plasma versus $\sim 18 \mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ in EAT and $\sim 8 \mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ SAT) and the elevated

OXCT1 (near-irreversible transfer of CoA from succinyl-CoA to acetoacetate) suggests that the ketolysis should still be the preferred direction. The degradation of branched-chain amino acids (BCAA) may generate intermediates that contribute to the production of ketone bodies, and the levels of all three amino acids, along with their degradation products, were found to be increased during the SHF state (Fig. S7). Lastly, the 3-OHB intermediate of impaired β -oxidation could be the source, namely the conversion of S-3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA to L-3-OHB catalyzed by acyl-CoA thioesterase (Fig. 4A).

However, two stereoisomers of 3-OHB exist: D-3-hydroxybutyrate (R-form) and L-3-hydroxybutyrate (S-form). The D-enantiomer is the one physiologically produced in the liver during ketogenesis from acetyl-CoA or BCAA, and the L-form is the intermediate of β -oxidation (Fig. 4A). Under basal conditions, the concentration of circulating D-3-OHB is approximately $100 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$, while L-3-OHB constitutes only 4% (approximately $4 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$) of the total 3-OHB [29]. To decipher which form is generated by the EAT explants, we had to separate the enantiomers (Fig. 5E). Quantification of the produced 3-OHB showed that the explants released high amounts of L-3-OHB (Fig. 5F), which contribute to the total 3-OHB levels up to 30%. Plasma concentrations of L-3-OHB were around 3%, as expected (Fig. 5G).

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. Peroxisomal and mitochondrial β - and ω -oxidation of fatty acids.

(A) Schematic representation of EAT metabolism. Major pathways of interest are highlighted in orange boxes. Fatty acids released by lipolysis are β - or ω -oxidized, and the resulting acetyl-CoA concentrates in the mitochondria. D-3-OHB, synthesized by the liver, can be degraded into acetyl-CoA (ketolysis) or theoretically synthesized from precursors via BCAA degradation. Impairment of β -oxidation in the last round of the pathway generates L-3-OHB. For genes, see Supplemental Table S1.

(B) Levels of mRNA for pathways depicted in (A) for SAT and EAT. Values are fold-changes over the control group. For a detailed map, see Fig. S3.

(C) Details of the marker genes for peroxisomal oxidation (*ACOX1*, *ACAA1*, *HSD17B4*). Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 19, 23, 40; 16, 20, 50$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(D) Levels of dicarboxylic acylcarnitines produced in peroxisomal oxidation. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(E) Dicarboxylic acylcarnitine with eight carbon atoms. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(F) Details of the marker genes for mitochondrial oxidation (*CTPIA*, *HADHA*) together with acylcarnitine (CAR 2:0). Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 19, 23, 40; 16, 20, 50$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(G) Levels of short-chain acylcarnitines: butyrylcarnitine, hydroxybutyrylcarnitine, acetylcarnitine. Data are means \pm S.D., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

4. Discussion

Our study provides a comprehensive metabolomic-based analysis of the dynamic metabolic changes in EAT and SAT during HF progression. The results highlight that although both depots undergo profound metabolic adaptations, EAT and SAT exhibit distinct trajectories in lipid metabolism, FA oxidation, and synthesis of 3-OHB. We describe here, for the first time, that the L-3-OHB is actively formed in EAT in patients with HF and can specifically support the metabolism of the heart muscle in more advanced phases of HFREF. Our findings, which indicate that 3-OHB is produced primarily during impaired fatty acid β -oxidation, are consistent with previous studies on rat adipose tissue showing acetoacetate formation but not 3-OHB from leucine [30]. These findings underscore depot-specific metabolic responses that may influence cardiac energy homeostasis and HF pathophysiology.

The relationship between adipose tissue and HFREF remains unresolved, appearing to be double-edged, as both excess and depletion of fat have been linked to adverse outcomes. This paradox underscores the need for further research to elucidate the impact of different fat depots on disease progression and prognosis in HFREF. Our findings in control subjects and patients with MHF are consistent with the general knowledge, which highlights that early stages of HF are characterized by a systemic metabolic imbalance, including insulin resistance, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and a shift toward catabolic dominance, but without overt tissue wasting or cachexia. However, our results on SHF groups do not simply extend the transition from a healthy state to MHF; the changes are more complex.

The dynamics of lipolysis in EAT and SAT are different. While the SAT represents a predictable situation of well-organized lipolysis combined with fine-tuned lipid synthesis, the EAT metabolomic profile represents a depot-specific setting focused on peroxisomal FA oxidation. However, the unique EAT metabolic profile fails to maintain the lipolytic pace during HF progression, resulting in the silencing of genes responsible for the peroxisomal FA oxidation and cell overload with peroxisomal FA oxidation intermediates. This can be explained by the exceptional metabolic turnover of FAs and glucose in EAT of monkeys and guinea pigs, where the rate of FA synthesis and breakdown was up to ~ 2.5 -fold higher, mitochondrial content comparable, and the glucose utilization about half that of the intra-abdominal depots [31]. EAT specialization in FA turnover makes it a suitable local FA buffering system, and peroxisomal FA oxidation is a form of metabolic adaptation to secure FA degradation with specifically well-tuned production of short-chain acyl-CoA, which fails when overloaded during HF.

The role of peroxisomal FA oxidation in EAT may be related to the greater substrate diversity that allows this depot to utilize very long-chain-, dicarboxylic-, and polyunsaturated FA. Peroxisomal β -oxidation also acts as a sensor for intracellular FA and regulates lipolysis by modulating adipose triglyceride lipase activity [32], which could dysregulate the sequential process of triacylglycerol lipolysis and shift the

time profile of the clusters per lipid class (Fig. 1). Reduced transcription of β -adrenergic and natriuretic peptide receptors likely reflects adipose tissue resistance to lipolytic stimuli, consistent with impaired metabolic flexibility in SHF. By contrast, preserved *INSR* expression suggests maintained insulin responsiveness. We therefore interpret these patterns as partially compensatory mechanisms aimed at relieving β -oxidation overload and keeping the high metabolic turnover [31]. Why only the EAT would rewire the pathways in this direction, and whether there is a hidden benefit for the heart or simple metabolic failure, remains unclear.

The failing heart exhibits changes in energy metabolism, characterized by reduced flexibility and efficiency in substrate utilization. Instead of primarily using free FA, it shifts to using glucose and other alternatives, such as lactate and ketone bodies generated by the liver [33–35], leading to an energy deficit that contributes to the severity of HF. However, our results suggest that EAT-derived L-3-OHB could also be involved. The accumulation of L-3-OHB in cardiac tissue is an intriguing and incompletely understood aspect of myocardial metabolism [29,36]. Heart tissue contains the highest fraction of L-3-OHB of any organ in the body: 34 % (38 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ tissue) of total 3-OHB, compared to only 2–4 % in plasma and liver [29,37]. However, the precise mechanisms, sources, and physiological purpose remain subjects of active investigation.

We speculate that the heart's high baseline FA oxidation rate (60–90 % of ATP from FAs) naturally leads to a byproduct, L-3-OHB. Myocardial oxidation of L-3-OHB, which needs an extra ATP to reenter β -oxidation, is very slow compared with D-3-OHB, which can directly flow toward the TCA cycle [29]. L-3-OHB may buffer CoA availability during metabolic stress or could represent a “reserve” form of carbon units for emergency energy production. L-3-OHB also exerts vasodilatory effects on both epicardial and microvascular coronary vessels similar to D-3-OHB, which reduces arterial elastance (afterload) and increases cardiac output [29,38]. Short-chain FAs like butyrate also outpace ketone oxidation in the failing heart, and the EAT can serve as a very specific source of L-3-OHB for the myocardium and coronary arteries (Fig. 6) [39].

3-OHB activates two G protein-coupled receptors with metabolic functions: HCAR2 (hydroxycarboxylic acid receptor 2, GPR109A) and FFAR3 (free fatty acid receptor 3, GPR41) on adipocytes [40]. The enantiomers differ in potency: D-3-OHB activates HCAR2 with an EC_{50} of 0.77 mM, whereas L-3-OHB requires 1.66 mM, marking a twofold difference significant at physiological ketone concentrations [41]. In adipocytes, HCAR2 activation suppresses catecholamine-driven lipolysis via adenylyl cyclase inhibition. Simultaneously, FFAR3 inhibition by 3-OHB further reduces lipolysis through Gi protein signaling [42]. These complementary anti-lipolytic mechanisms suggest that both enantiomers may exert strong metabolic restraint in EAT.

With respect to the effects on the heart, Nielsen and colleagues observed beneficial hemodynamic effects of racemic 3-OHB administration in HFREF patients [43]. Van Rijt and colleagues conducted

Fig. 5. Ketone body metabolism in plasma and adipose tissue depots.

(A) Levels of total 3-OHB, acetoacetate, and non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) in plasma. Data are means \pm S.E., $n = 34, 45, 121$; *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test.

(B) Levels of total 3-OHB in SAT and EAT. Data are means \pm S.E., $n = 34, 44, 111; 30, 41, 76$. *Statistically significant difference at $p < 0.05$, one-way ANOVA/Tukey test for each adipose depot.

(C) Levels of total 3-OHB released into media by EAT explants after 60 and 90 min of incubation.

(D) Chromatograms of OHB isomers (m/z 103.0395), analytical standards (blue), and EAT sample.

(E) Chromatograms of 3-OHB enantiomers (m/z 241.1910 > m/z 197.1654), analytical standards (blue), and EAT explant media sample.

(F) Percent of L-3-OHB in the EAT explant and corresponding medium after 90 min of incubation; extension of panel C.

(G) Percent of L-3-OHB in plasma. Data are means \pm S.E., $n = 30, 42, 103$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

pharmacokinetic studies in patients with multiple acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency and in healthy rats receiving oral racemic D/L-3-OHB [44]. They demonstrated that oral D/L-3-OHB administration caused substantially higher L-3-OHB concentrations than D-3-OHB in blood. Rat tissue distribution analyses showed that L-3-OHB concentrations increased extensively in brain, heart, liver, and muscle, whereas D-3-OHB increases were most pronounced in heart and liver, implying differential metabolic fates for the two forms. The only published enantiomer-specific trial comparing L-3-OHB and D-3-OHB is the randomized crossover study in pigs, which demonstrated that L-3-OHB produces stronger hemodynamic effects than D-3-OHB due to slower whole-body metabolism and higher circulating levels, despite minimal myocardial uptake, whereas D-3-OHB is rapidly metabolized by the

heart but produces weaker cardiovascular effects [29]. From the clinical perspective, the L-3-OHB might serve as a supplementary fuel for the myocardium, although the heart can produce L-3-OHB itself, or as a signaling, slower-acting molecule triggering beneficial hemodynamic response.

Hepatic D-3-OHB production is increased during HF, and the concentration gradient drives uptake in extrahepatic tissues [27,45]. Although we did not perform a tracer dilution experiment with ¹³C-labeled D-3-OHB, the release of D-3-OHB from the explants is most likely a passive process driven by accumulated metabolites, as the coronary arteries transport fuel toward the myocardium through the EAT layer. A significant part of the SHF group was treated with gliflozins, which also increase D-3-OHB systemic levels [18]. This increase was observed only

Fig. 6. Schematic summary of the EAT metabolism within the heart.

(A) Scheme of the heart illustrating the position of EAT within the epicardium.

(B) Schematic flow of D-3-OHB (white path) from the liver through the heart into the coronary arteries. EAT produces L-3-OHB (black), which is distributed via the coronary arteries to the myocardium together with D-3-OHB from the liver.

in plasma and not in the adipose tissue, supporting the exclusive L-3-OHB production by EAT (Fig. S8).

Our results show clear differences between the two adipose tissue depots during HF progression. While EAT is a relatively small patch of specialized adipose tissue located on the failing heart, SAT samples represent the core adipose tissue responding to lipolytic demands. What is the exact purpose of the metabolic rewiring of EAT, and whether preserving its metabolic function in the late stages of HF could help the heart remains to be determined.

4.1. Clinical perspectives

EAT can produce significant amounts of L-3-OHB in heart failure, with levels rising further in advanced stages. This depot-derived synthesis of a short-chain fatty acid, an enantiomer of ketone body D-3-OHB, may help support cardiac energy needs as the failing heart loses metabolic flexibility and shifts toward alternative fuels.

4.2. Limitations of the study

The analysis did not include HFpEF, so the results may not apply to this patient group, which has different underlying mechanisms. The cross-sectional study design compared MHF and SHF in separate groups of subjects. As a result, pseudo-time profiles were constructed under the assumption that MHF progresses to SHF. However, this does not reflect a true natural history study with longitudinal follow-up of the same individuals. Not all measurements were available for every subject, though there was no evidence of selection bias related to missing data. Additionally, the study did not include body composition analysis, which limits the assessment of the role of muscle mass and other body compartments. Only EAT and SAT adipose tissues were evaluated; other fat depots, such as visceral or perivascular adipose tissue, were not studied. No volumetric EAT data were acquired. The LIMeX approach does not determine the localization and geometry of the double bond within FAs or other lipid species. 3-OHB within the profiling part was not separated into the D- and L-form.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization: VM, MH, OK; Data curation: MR, BJK, MV, PJ, EH, KA, KK; Formal Analysis: MR, BJK, MV, PJ, EH, KA, KK, TC; Funding acquisition: VM, MH, OK; Investigation: MR, BJK, MV, PJ, EH, KA, PI, DH, KK, JK, STH, MM, OK; Methodology: BJK, MV, VM, MH, OK; Project administration: JK, IN, MH, OK; Resources: PI, DH, TC, JK, STH, MM, IN, VM, OK; Software: MV, OK; Supervision: VM, MH, OK; Validation: MR, STH, MM, VM, OK; Visualization: MR, MV, OK; Writing – original draft: MR, BJK, MV, VM, OK; Writing – review & editing: MR, BJK, MV, PJ, EH, KA, PI, DH, KK, TC, JK, STH, MM, IN, VM, MH, OK.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metabol.2025.156465>.

Data availability

De-identified data supporting this study are available upon request from the corresponding author, subject to data sharing agreements and ethical approval to ensure patient privacy protection.

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